

Biography: James C. Cavender

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Abstract: Dr. James Cavender is a world authority on the diversity and ecology of dictyostelid cellular slime molds (“dictyostelids”) and professor emeritus at Ohio University in Athens, Ohio, USA. He has traveled the globe solo and with various teams of colleagues, students, and family to discover new species of dictyostelids and to understand their ecology and evolution. Cavender has made major contributions to their isolation methods, taxonomic identification, ecology and systematics over six decades. He has also been a dedicated teacher of mycology, alternative agriculture, tropical botany, medicinal plants, soils and uses of plants by indigenous cultures. Throughout his career, he has mentored students to incorporate the microbial world in their endeavors both within and beyond academia and also to appreciate the intrinsic value of nature.

Keywords: field biology, laboratory techniques, scientific influence.

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Education and Background

Over the course of his research career James Cavender (Fig. 1) published widely on the ecological distribution, taxonomy and evolution of dictyostelids—a monophyletic group of sorocarp-forming social amoebae in the major eukaryotic division Amoebozoa. Cavender published more than 130 papers in peer-reviewed journals and book chapters, most of them dedicated to the dictyostelid cellular slime molds. Dictyostelids comprise almost 200 described species and are common in terrestrial soils globally (Perrigo et al. 2020). They inhabit the soil and leaf litter of ecosystems, primarily forests but also grasslands, where they feed mostly on bacteria.

Dictyostelids (Fig. 2) are referred to as both “cellular slime molds” and “social amoebae.” Cellular slime molds are actually amoebae, not fungi, and only distantly related to the other “plasmodial or acellular slime molds,” the myxomycetes. Dictyostelids have a unique form of sociality in which single-celled feeding amoebae undergo a biochemically coordinated aggregation to form a multicellular sporulation structure, the sorocarp. They have been studied intensively as a model to understand the evolution of multicellularity. Early publications refer to the class of cellular slime molds as the Acrasidae, a name now outdated given recent molecular-based revisions to dictyostelid phylogenetic relationships.

Cavender had tremendous respect for his advisor, Kenneth Raper, who began work on the ecological distribution of dictyostelids. He also admired John Bonner, a world expert on cellular slime molds at Princeton (Figure 3d).

Figure 1. James C. Cavender. A) in Trinidad ca 1975, B) photographing dictyostelids on a light microscope in his lab (photo courtesy of Ohio University), C) in the Swiss Alps hosted by Hans Hohl at the University of Zurich during a sabbatical ca 1981, D) in Central America collecting soil samples for cellular slime mold extraction ca 1992, E) at the OU prairie restoration site he established in Athens, Ohio, 2015.

“Aside from putting dictyostelid cellular slime molds on the global biodiversity map for over 60 years, Dr. Cavender instilled in his students a deep appreciation for the profundities of Nature,” writes Terry Henkel, a former undergraduate student, colleague and friend of 46 years and now a mycology professor at Cal Poly Humboldt. Cavender taught generations of students to grow food sustainably, to collect and identify fungi, to understand the importance of soil and the microbial world, to understand the medicinal and traditional uses of plants, to examine human interactions with plants, and to gain insights into the flora, culture and ancient history of indigenous America.

Growing up close to nature on a small lake in rural New Jersey and later on a small dairy farm in upstate New York near the Vermont border, Cavender and his twin brother Ted both had a strong early interest in the natural world. These earlier experiences were critical to his life-long interactions with nature. Cavender studied biology at Union College in Schenectady NY, where his professor Bill Winne was important in stimulating his interest in plants and the natural world. He subsequently went to graduate school at the University of Wisconsin-Madison to work with Dr. Kenneth Raper.

Cavender had been interested in soil fungi, particularly mycorrhiza, and Raper told him about the cellular slime mold work he was doing and convinced him to join his lab. There he met other lifelong colleagues, including Hans Hohl (University of Zurich) and Theo Konijn (Wageningen University). At UW-Madison, Raper encouraged him to work outside of the lab and arranged his first collecting trip to Costa Rica and funded his first trip to Mexico. He completed his Ph.D. in 1963 and stayed on for a one year post-doc in Raper's lab. He met Andrée Battiste at UW-Madison, and they married in 1965. They had three children (Danielle, Jeannine and Nicole).

He started his first teaching position at Wabash College in Crawfordsville, Indiana, where he stayed five years. At Wabash he worked closely with fellow biologist Bob Petty, a lover of mushrooms, who became a close friend. Cavender started at Ohio University (OU) in Athens, Ohio in the Department of Botany in 1970. On an introductory visit, Prof. Art Blicke explained what a wonderful university OU was and a terrific environment to work in. Cavender is currently emeritus professor there. He was an avid long-distance runner and enjoyed gardening and physical work. At 88, he now has seven grandchildren and still lives in Athens, Ohio while exercising nearly every day, particularly swimming, and enjoying the sunshine whenever it appears at Dow Lake.

Research and Publications

His six decade publication history spanned his early foundational papers on the Acrasiae in *Nature* (Cavender and Raper 1965a, b, c), developing their isolation methods, establishing forests as primary habitat and documenting their occurrence and distribution in eastern North America (1963-1965) to relatively recent collaborative papers (2018-2022) on the distribution of dictyostelids in South Africa (Cavender et al. 2018), Madagascar (Cavender et al. 2021) and Thailand (Fig. 2, Vadell et al. 2018). When Cavender began working on his Ph.D. in the early 1960s, only about 30 species of cellular slime molds had been discovered. His development of a quantitative method for dictyostelid isolation from soil samples (Cavender and Raper 1965a), made possible ecological studies based on frequency and density of occurrence. These methods became a standard for the field and enabled consistent quantification across sites around the globe.

“The 1965 Cavender & Raper papers are the classics which laid out the methods for effective dictyostelid isolation from soil, which have been used by everybody (including myself) ever since,” says Henkel, “and are the first to show linkages between plant and soil microbial community compositions.” This early work created the foundation for all of his subsequent work discovering and describing around 150 new species, together with students and collaborators to understand dictyostelid ecology and evolution.

Steve Stephenson from the University of Arkansas, his research collaborator and coauthor over 25 years, refers to the numerous species of dictyostelids described by Cavender as “more than anyone else (by far!).” Henkel elaborates, “work from the Great Smoky Mountains is an important example” (Cavender et al. 2005) “as is Cavender and Raper 1968, which described the first (and still only) dictyostelids from Guyana.”

A series of global expeditions laid the foundation for determining the phylogenetic relationships of the social amoebae (Romeralo et al. 2011) and the evolution of their form, function and type of multicellularity (Schaap et al. 2006). First author Pauline Schaap writes of Cavender: “his discovery of so many species of [dictyostelids] and his meticulous description of these species has been of enormous importance for the [dictyostelid] field in general and more so for my own work in trying to resolve questions about the evolution of the particular type of multicellularity that they display.” He was fortunate to have been part of a major collaboration led by Stephenson with collaborator John Landolt and European colleagues Sandra Baldauf and Pauline Schaap. In 2018, the dictyostelids were reclassified based on molecular systematics evidence. Both a genus and a family were named after Cavender (Sheikh et al. 2018).

Figure 2. *Cavenderia bhumiboliana*, a dictyostelid cellular slime mold from Thailand. A) Aggregations. B) Sorogens. C) Sorocarps. D) Bases. E) Tips. F) Spores. G) Myxamoebae. Scale bars: a,b: 300 µm; c: 0.5 mm; d: 20 µm; e: 10 µm; f: 6 µm; g: 10 µm. Reprinted from Vadell et al. (2018) with permission under a CC by 4.0 license.

Expeditions

In addition to collecting dictyostelids throughout the United States and Canada, he made a series of expeditions over six decades that crisscrossed the globe. These were funded by various sources, including the National Science Foundation and the American Philosophical Society. In early years, he traveled to Mexico four times by car, sometimes with his brother, an ichthyologist and Professor Emeritus at Ohio State, and later to other parts of Mesoamerica. He also traveled across Canada, the southwestern US, the Great Smoky Mountains, the Rocky Mountains, the Florida Everglades, Alaska, Puerto Rico and the Virgin Islands.

Over the length of his career, Cavender criss-crossed the globe spanning five continents and numerous countries to discover arctic, temperate and tropical dictyostelids over both altitudinal and latitudinal gradients, including Costa Rica, Belize, Honduras, Guatemala, Colombia, Guyana, Argentina (Patagonia), Central African Republic, Kenya, Tanzania, South Africa, India, Japan, Southeast Asia (including Indonesia and Hong Kong), Trinidad and Tobago, the Bahamas, Iceland, Denmark, Switzerland, Germany, France, Italy, Spain, Portugal and the former Yugoslavia. In recent years, Cavender also isolated, described, and published on dictyostelids from Thailand, Madagascar, Australia and New Zealand, but collaborators collected those sample soils in his place; “too much for me” he said.

In his work in Japan, he and his collaborators discovered new species by searching in the undisturbed forests around ancient temples. Graduate student Eduardo Vadell worked with him on an in-depth study of the dictyostelids at Tikal, Guatemala (Vadell et al. 1995) and became a life-long collaborator. In newly reunified Germany in 1992, Cavender collaborated with daughter Jeannine Cavender-Bares on a study of the slime molds in German forests. Cavender and Cavender-Bares, who was living in Germany at the time, sampled the majority of Germany's forested regions from west to east with support from Hans Hohl, a dictyostelid expert at the University of Zurich (Cavender et al. 1995).

In isolated forest remnants in southeast Ohio within a reclaimed strip mine and ecotourism destination called the Wilds, Cavender and daughter Nicole Cavender, who was then Director of Restoration Ecology at the Wilds, found more species of dictyostelids than in the rest of Ohio combined (Cavender and Cavender 2013). This work expanded earlier work led by his student Chris Hopka. Nicole also collaborated on field work in the Virgin Islands (Cavender et al. 2004) and South Africa (Cavender et al. 2018).

Cavender was fortunate to collaborate on larger discovery grants led by Steve Stephenson, who studies myxomycetes, the “other” slime molds. They traveled to Tierra del Fuego and Patagonia in January and February of 2005 (Fig. 3b). Cavender explains, “Stephenson [who is a global leader in the study of myxomycetes] was good at getting grants.” This work spanned a major shift for Cavender from solo and teacher-student based science to team science. An important lesson he expressed from his collaborative work was to see the different roles people play in team science and how much more can be accomplished by a team than by individuals working alone.

While collaboration was important to him, in earlier years there were few other colleagues working on the diversity of dictyostelids. He joined forces with Hans Hohl at the University of Zurich, and traveled to Japan to work with Hiromitsu Hagiwara and Kunihiko Kawabe (Cavender and Kawabe 1989). He also traveled to India to work with T. N. Lakhanpal in the Himalayas (Cavender and Lakhanpal 1986). He

joined efforts with colleagues Steve Stephenson and John Landolt. Stephenson obtained large grants to build teams so that they could collectively get to more areas.

He also collaborated with molecular systematists, advancing the evolutionary ecology of the dictyostelids (Schaap et al. 2006, Romeralo et al. 2007). He investigated the latitudinal distribution of dictyostelids (Swanson et al. 1999), at a time when large-scale analyses that could lead to generalities in the microbial realm were challenging. Advancing early treatment of the geographical distribution of dictyostelids (Cavender 1973) and Raper's publication in 1984 of his book "The Dictyostelids," Cavender's graduate student, Andrew Swanson, published one of the first studies of the global distribution of a microbial lineage (Swanson et al. 1999). This was followed by the volume "Dictyostelids" edited by Romeralo et al. in 2013 in which Cavender provided an updated overview of dictyostelid ecology.

Figure 3. A) James Cavender leading a tropical botany course in Belize, ca 1990 with Michael Holmes (graduate student) and Hank Huggins (undergraduate student); photo credit: Andrew Swanson (former grad student). B) Eumycetozoan collecting group expedition to Patagonia and Tierra del Fuego; Perito Moreno Glacier, Argentina, 2005: James Cavender (front left), Steve Stephenson (center front), Fred Spiegel (right front), Eduardo Vadell (left back), Diana Wrigley de Basanta (center back), Carlos Lado (right back) and others. C) James Cavender with his twin brother Ted Cavender ca 2000. D) James Cavender with the late John Bonner, mycology professor and cellular slime mold expert, at Princeton University in 2008.

Cavender felt enormous gratitude toward the collaborative community when the family Cavenderiaceae and genus *Cavenderia* of the dictyostelids were named after him (Scheikh et al. 2018), recognizing his lifelong contributions to the study of the microbial world and the diversity of life.

Teaching and Mentoring

Cavender trained and mentored many students who developed successful careers outside of academia grounded in plants, fungi and soil. Nicknames they often called him ranged from “Jim”, “Cav”, “Cavvy”, “Cavender” to “The Doc”. He taught a range of courses (Table 1), taking advantage of Ohio University's quarter system at the time and strong emphasis on teaching. He considers one of his most important contributions to be teaching Tropical Botany, a course in which he yearly took students to Belize and Guatemala to learn about plants and human culture. He led this course together with former student Mark Cohen, who established the Belize Agroforestry Research Center with support from Cavender and others.

Table 1. List of major courses taught by James Cavender at Ohio University.

Courses taught	Brief summary
<i>Alternative Agriculture</i>	A course of theory and practice to grow food for health and sustainability. Students planned, planted and worked gardens located at the Ohio Student Farm.
<i>Mycology</i>	Introductory study of fungi, including a field component on mushrooms
<i>Dictyostelids</i>	Graduate level course on cellular slime molds
<i>Medicinal Plants</i>	Field course on herbs, often taught in the summer
<i>Plants and People</i>	Freshman course (something everyone taught)
<i>Introductory Botany</i>	Introduction to botany
<i>Soils</i>	Introduction to soil science – field and lab components
<i>Origins</i>	Human history in deep time with an emphasis on indigenous cultures, particularly the way the Native Americans lived before European settlement
<i>Tropical Botany</i>	Taught during winter quarter during field trips to Belize, Guatemala and sometimes Honduras.

According to his departmental colleague at Ohio University, James Braselton, “his legacy at Ohio University, and in the Department of Environmental & Plant Biology, probably will be what is now known as the Ohio Student Farm and West State Street Research Site. Through hard work and gentle, polite stubbornness he was able to overcome resistance from several levels of administration at the University to transform an [underutilized] piece of land on West State Street into what has become a productive, instructional and research facility...Jim introduced ‘alternative agriculture’ to the University through a course that he originated and that was the driving force for establishing the West State Street garden.”

Braselton elaborates, “Something that Jim emphasized in his teachings, and that has stayed with me over the years, has been the importance of maintaining healthy soils for agriculture and the family garden. His knowledge of the microorganisms that live in the various types soils around the world was important in showing others how maintaining a healthy soil depends on maintaining the organisms that live in it.”

Charlotte Wachtel, a former undergraduate student and artist (involved *inter alia* in the “Women of Appalachia Project”) recalls the day in 1977 when she walked into her first class with Cavender on human interactions with plants (or *Plants and Man* as it was called then), “It only took that single hour to change the course of my college career and my entire life.” Wachtel writes:

“Compelling was the window on the world of nature Dr. Cavender opened. A world of glory and chaos, abundance and complexity, beauty and fundamental order, with [humans] as only a small part of the whole picture... Whether it was learning the names and uses of the culinary and medicinal herbs, contemplating the *Tao Te Ching*, or mixing flour, water and fungi to make bread, I was inspired. I wanted to know MORE. That inspiration and motivation is what college classes should foster, and Dr. Cavender's did.”

Over his teaching career, he took students on innumerable field trips throughout the region collecting herbs and mushrooms, understanding soils and learning about plants and their uses. He started the circular teaching garden at OU, where students work together to grow a diversity of food plants in wedge shaped garden beds, double dug, without pesticides or chemical fertilizers. He was also passionate about prairie restoration and restored small prairies on campus and on his own land next to the Wayne National Forest. He taught and conducted research at OU for 35 years before transitioning to emeritus status in 2004, allowing him to complete his research efforts.

Cavender trained a wide array of students in alternative agriculture, microbes and soil biology (Fig. 2). Former graduate student Eduardo Vadell wrote: “In his courses and laboratory everyone was welcomed, whatever their origin or belief.” Some of his former students became academics while others developed applied careers in the realm of soil and agriculture. Several started businesses or nonprofits that involve organic and regenerative agriculture, using bacteria in soil for farming, medicinal plants, growing mushrooms, and prairie restoration. As a professor, he was noted for giving hard exams, being a stickler for details but also having compassion and recognizing talent when he saw it. Writes former student, Terry Henkel:

“When I took Dr. Cavender's mycology class at OU, for the final exam the one thing I didn't study fully was the ascomycete life cycle. I knew that either the basidiomycete or the ascomycete life cycle was going to be on the exam but gambled that it would be the basidio life cycle, but it wasn't. Since I knew the basidio life cycle inside and out, I diagrammed that out instead. When I got the graded exam back, Dr. C gave me full credit for the answer because it was perfectly done, even though it wasn't what he asked for. Because of this empathetic move from the professor, I got an A in the course. He won't remember this, but I do! I still have the graded exam lol.”

Table 2. Partial list of former undergraduate and graduate students (mostly Master's) who went on to careers in botany, mycology, microbiology and environmental sciences in academia, government, nonprofits or the private sector.

Student	Years	Current or primary position
Chris Hopka	Master's student mid-1970s	Master grower and owner of Drumlin Nurseries, UW-Madison extension, Madison, Wisconsin
Martha Bishop	Undergrad student 1970s	Instructor and Lab coordinator, Environmental & Plant Biology Department, Ohio University
Ed Newman	Undergrad student 1975-1981	Zero waste special projects director for Rural Action; Bee inspector for Athens and Meigs counties, Ohio
Thomas Volk	Undergrad student 1976-1980	Department of Biology, UW-LaCrosse (deceased)
Terry Henkel	Undergrad student 1978-1983	Department of Biological Sciences, Cal Poly Humboldt
Mark Cohen	Undergrad student 1978-1980	Agraria Center for Regenerative Practice, Ohio www.agrariacenter.org
Charlotte Wachtel	Undergrad student late 1970s, early 80s	Artist, Women of Appalachia Project
Charles Hammer	Undergrad and Master's student 1975-1979; 1982-1984	Projects Manager, The Hammer Family Farm; former County Health Commissioner in several Ohio counties
Gary Kauffman	Undergrad student Master's student 1970s, 1980s	Botanist, USDA Forest Service, North Carolina
Susan Calhoun	Undergrad student 1979-1985	Landscape Coordinator and manager of campus trees and landscapes, Ohio University
Eric Miller	Undergrad student 1980s	Science teacher, Athens High School, Athens Public Schools
Barbara Ballard	Ph.D. student 1979-1984	Professor, Biological Sciences, Marymount University, Virginia
Eduardo Vadell	Master's student Ph.D. student 1980s	Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales, University of Buenos Aires, Argentina
Scott Maris	Master's student 1982-1984	President, Julian Environmental Group, LLC
Andrew Swanson	Master's student 1990s	Professor, Department of Natural Science, State College of Florida
Michael Holmes	Master's student early 1990s	Chief Operating Officer and Founder, Holmes ENVIRO, LLC, Oregon https://holmesenviro.net/
Nicole Cavender	Undergrad student 1992-1996	Director, Huntington Botanical Garden, Pasadena
Hank Huggins	Undergrad student 1990s	Co-founder and co-owner, Land Reformers nursery business

Bill Shores	Master's student 1995-1997	Garden Writer, Consultant, and Educator; Founder Urban Edibles, Chicago
George Vaughan	Undergrad and Master's student 1995-1997	President, Mushroom Harvest, Oregon www.mushroomharvest.com
James Spurney	Master's student 1996-1999	Horticulture industry, native arboretum manager, Athens, Ohio

In his own words, “taking the kids down to Belize and Guatemala and Belize was my major contribution... it was a pretty monumental undertaking.” “I thought it would help save the rainforest if more people got acquainted with it...I wanted students to see how people live there... I have a lot of memories from that.” In 1996, Ohio University honored him for “outstanding academic advising to students.”

He also immersed his daughters in the natural world and exposed them to the world of plants, fungi, soil, slime molds and gardening. His daughter Danielle Heskett, an accountant and financial planner, recalls camping in the rain, sun or snow in remote places, where we learned to become comfortable feeling uncomfortable. He mentored all three of us on numerous science fair projects, setting two of us up for careers in the botanical sciences. Daughter Nicole Cavender was a botany major at OU and took nearly all of his classes. As a child, she recalls, “Sometimes he would have me pick up a handful of soil or compost and smell it or rub the soil through my fingers so that I could feel it. At the time, I wasn't really sure what I was learning. It seemed a bit odd. Now, after many years of picking up soil, I have a good idea of how rich the soil is just by its feel and odor. It's an important tool for gardening, an activity in which I have learned to love.” Nicole is now the Director of the Huntington Botanical Garden in Pasadena, California.

His colleague and former Dean, Brian McCarthy, wrote about his teaching: “One thing that stuck with me was something that a student related to me on 9/11. Apparently, the mycology class was preparing to go out on a field trip. There was a lot of chatter about the first plane crashing into the World Trade Center and the students felt uncomfortable. He decided to go anyway. What I took from this was that being out in the woods doing what you love to do is probably the best antidote to most problems in life.”

His former student, Andrew Swanson, now a professor at the State College of Florida said, “Aside from my parents, Jim had the single greatest influence on the trajectory and quality of my life. I am indebted.” Says Henkel, “Those of us who tapped into the "Cavenderian world view" as students at OU have carried these teachings with us, and they have guided our work and life choices, ever since.” Students like Andrew Swanson recall his disappearing tricks, “Where did he go?”, particularly when seeking morel mushrooms to avoid revealing their secret locations. Wachtel recalls him standing on his head, one of his yoga postures, before class. A favorite stunt of his was to eat poison ivy, which he demonstrated in his medicinal plants class. His mentoring style was one of tough love. As Charles Hammer recalls, “In his lab, when I'd hit a wall, he'd more often than not allow me to struggle with it. As a young man, that was high value training. It didn't take me too long to appreciate it.”

Personal life

Growing up, Cavender (my Dad) lived by a large pond in Mahwah, New Jersey with his family. He fished and explored nearly every day with his identical twin brother, Ted Cavender, until the age of 13. His father was a physicist, trained at UW-Madison, who initially worked for Bell Labs in New York City and later for Western Electric. His mother had a master's in literature from UW-Madison. In the post-war years, they moved to a small dairy farm in upstate NY near the Vermont border to work towards his father's vision of living in a sustainable manner grounded by growing their own food and living off the land. The family's discipline and work ethic helped them navigate a challenging transition to subsistence farming. James (and Ted) attended Union College in Schenectady NY, which opened up the world of botany. They both ran track and cross country, fostering a lifelong passion for long-distance running. Ted became a professor at the Ohio State University (Fig. 3c). Their older brother, John Cavender III, became an eye doctor.

His steady disciplined research style matched his demeanor as a lifelong distance runner. He was physically very active his entire life, which contributed to his enthusiasm for long hikes in remote areas to obtain dictyostelids. He ran the annual Athens, Ohio Marathon, training for and completing thirteen consecutive marathons. My Mom would bring him sweet tea at the 20-mile mark, and I would sometimes join for the last six miles to provide moral support. Many of his students were running or hiking companions. His athleticism enabled him to hike into remote areas of the globe and persist with few comforts—from the Alps of Switzerland to East Africa.

Dad is a dedicated father and loyal husband. My mother, who passed in 2020, was the love of his life. They were married for over 55 years (m.1965). She traveled with him to many destinations. He loved the rolling hills of Athens, the fascinating geology of the region and nature all around. Athens is an extraordinary intersection of nature with a rich intellectual culture and strong sense of community. He appreciated life in a small university town where one is known well by the community, where folks meet at the local farmers market and help each other through challenging times.

My Mom called my Dad an iconoclast who was ahead of his time. He appreciated and taught about medicinal plants and alternative agriculture, held sweat lodges at his cabin next to Wayne National Forest—built by hand with the help of numerous students. He practiced yoga and meditation long before it was widespread. I have childhood memories sitting in an auditorium listening to Ram Dass when I was a kid, stopping at the Omega Institute in NY, and riding horseback in Kansas at the Land Institute, where we visited with alternative agriculture pioneer Wes Jackson and his family.

He lived much of his life through his adventures with cellular slime molds. We spent many summers traveling across different regions of the US or Canada by car, usually in a VW bug or a VW bus, hiking through remote landscapes (Fig. 4). Our “family vacations” always involved collecting soil samples, camping everywhere we went, even in the rain or in very isolated areas with no running water, often en route to a scientific conference as a final destination. He always had his collecting bag and a cooler along for soil samples. For him it was a way of life. I recall climbing a mountain with him in Snowmass Colorado during the 1980 Rocky Mountain Mushroom conference, having driven west from Athens, Ohio, and camping along the way. On that trip, we visited the medicine wheel in Wyoming, which inspired his design of the circle garden within the Ohio University Student Farm, where he taught alternative agriculture to a generation of students.

Our mother traveled with him to places like Trinidad and Tobago, Indonesia, Switzerland and Belize. When our parents traveled to Southeast Asia, we stayed with grandparents and cousins. Later, my sister Nicole and I would also join him for some of the Tropical Botany course trips in Central America. He cajoled both of us to collaborate on manuscripts with him. Despite his lifelong commitment, persistence and consistency, he never overworked. Somehow, he finished everything he set out to do.

Figure 4. A) Family camping trip ‘out west’ near the Black Hills of South Dakota, 1980; B) Family hike in the Great Smoky Mountains ca 1975; C) Daughters Danielle, Jeannine and Nicole in an oak tree ca 1978; D) James Cavender and daughter Jeannine on a hike in the Rocky Mountains, 1980; E) Andrée Cavender (wife), daughter Nicole and James at a high school track meet ca 1989; F) James and Andrée Cavender, 1997.

Conclusions

It is hard to capture a life in a short biography. Cavender has made worthwhile use of his “one wild and precious life,” to use the words of Mary Oliver, to discover tiny organisms whose ecological importance is profound but poorly understood. Writes Eduardo Vadell, “Austerity, humbleness, silence and sense of humor, perseverance, constancy and honesty distinguish him and his work from that of many other scientists of our time.” Some of his published works, won at great expense with incredible athletic and scientific rigor, have been cited only a handful of times. Yet in some of these cases he isolated and described new species that have never again been recovered. He developed culture collections, preserving these specimens by lyophilization, adding to the collection started by Kenneth Raper. Collectively, his

work has laid the foundation for deciphering the dictyostelid tree of life, helping to develop a model organism that serves as the basis for studying the evolution of multicellularity and enhancing understanding of the ecological importance of the microbial world. A relatively small number of colleagues shared his passion during the bulk of his career, but his long-term collaborations, which were in many cases also long-term friendships, were critical for completing the body of work. That work contributes to the accumulated body of knowledge of life on Earth. One can readily see he realized his vision of quantifying the global distribution of a microbial organism. More than this, he spent his life trying to teach students to live from and love the Earth. These students (Table 2) have gone off in many directions applying their knowledge, creativity and wisdom to teach others, bringing their vigor to academia, the private sector, to the NGO world, to governance and to lasting fulfilment in their private lives.

I will close with an excerpt from a letter I wrote him in June 2020 for Father's Day:

“Thank you for being my life long inspiration and mentor. Thank you for teaching me about nature and the beauty and healing powers of plants, the images of which fill my oldest memories. Thank you for showing me Indian Mounds in hidden places and showing me how to find mushrooms. Thank you for teaching me to walk quietly through the forest. Thank you for teaching me to love giant trees and tiny slime molds. Thank you for teaching me how to garden and to run fast and long distances. Thank you for encouraging me to draw and paint and to be creative. Thank you for practicing your weird yoga and meditation—which is no longer weird—and giving me that as a model and source of strength. Thank you for teaching me the importance of discipline and hard work. And the importance of not working too hard. Thank you for giving me the gift of books. Thank you for bringing me to Belize and Guatemala during your class trips and showing me another way to be. Thank you for reading my papers and caring about my work. Thank you for showing up in my life in all the ways that you have.”

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